

The Effect of Tour Guides' Communication Effectiveness on Tourists' Intercultural Interaction Levels*

Turist Rehberlerinin İletişim Etkinliğinin Turistlerin Kültürlerarası Etkileşim Düzeylerine Etkisi*

Araştırma Makalesi/Research Article

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Abstract

Key Words

Tour Guide,
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The primary aim of this study is to reveal the effect of tour guides' communication effectiveness on tourists' intercultural interaction levels, specifically within the context of incoming tours. In this regard, the study intended to analyze the effects of tour guides' communication effectiveness on intercultural interaction, the dependent variable, using scientific methods. The data collection tool used in the study was designed for both digital use via the Google Forms platform and for physical use. Accordingly, the data collection process was carried out in two formats: face-to-face interviews conducted by the researcher and Google Forms. In line with the research objective, data were collected from 263 participants using a survey. The analysis results revealed that tour guides' communication effectiveness positively influences tourists' intercultural interaction. Detailed analyses further confirmed a positive and significant effect on the sub-dimensions of intercultural interaction: emotional orientation, self-efficacy, and behavioral performance.

Anahtar Kelimeler

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Bu araştırmanın temel amacı; turist rehberlerinin sahip olduğu iletişim etkinliğinin, turistlerin kültürlerarası etkileşim düzeylerine etkisini incoming (gelen) turlar özelinde ortaya koymaktır. Bu bağlamda çalışmada turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin bağımlı değişken olan kültürlerarası etkileşim üzerindeki etkilerinin bilimsel yöntemlerle analiz edilmesi hedeflenmiştir. Çalışma kapsamında kullanılan veri toplama aracı hem Google Forms platformu üzerinden dijital olarak hem de fiziksel olarak tasarlanmıştır. Bu bağlamda araştırma verilerinin toplanması süreci, araştırmacının katılımcılarla yüz yüze görüşme yapması ve Google Forms platformu olmak üzere iki farklı formatta gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma amacı doğrultusunda 263 katılımcıdan anket tekniği ile veri elde edilmiştir. Araştırma verilerinin analizi sonucunda, incoming turlarla Türkiye'ye gelen turistlerin rehberli turlara katılımları durumunda turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin, turistlerin kültürlerarası etkileşimini olumlu yönde etkilediği saptanmıştır. Gerçekleştirilen detaylı analizlerde kültürlerarası etkileşim bağlamında duygusal yönelim, öz yeterlilik ve davranışsal performans alt boyutları bağlamında turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin turistlerin kültürlerarası etkileşimleri üzerinde olumlu ve anlamlı bir etkiye sahip olduğu saptanmıştır.

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Introduction

In today's world, where travel opportunities are becoming increasingly widespread, tourism has evolved from being merely an economic activity into one of the most important tools for intercultural dialogue and social interaction. In this environment where individuals from diverse cultures come together, tour guides who are regarded as cultural bridge-builders play a central role in the tourism experience (Ap and Wong, 2001). Tour guides do more than simply convey the historical, cultural, and natural values of the destinations they visit; they also lead the way in fostering an environment of interaction between the host community and tourists, grounded in understanding, empathy, and respect (Weiler and Black, 2015). This role elevates the profession of tourist guiding far beyond that of a mere information-sharing occupation, positioning it as a dynamic practitioner of intercultural communication.

Communication skills stand out as one of the core competencies of the tour guiding profession. No matter how extensive a guide's knowledge may be, the quality of the tour experience is significantly diminished if that knowledge cannot be effectively carried to the audience (Zhang and Chow, 2004). Effective communication is a multidimensional skill that extends beyond clear, understandable language to encompass body language, empathy, audience awareness, and cultural sensitivity (Chen and Starosta, 1996). The extent to which tour guides demonstrate this skill directly determines the experience tourists develop throughout the tour and the depth of their interactions with diverse cultures. In this context, communication effectiveness functions as a key variable that facilitates intercultural interaction.

The concept of intercultural interaction refers to the awareness, sensitivity, and adaptability that individuals develop toward distinct cultural value systems, belief systems, and behavioral norms. Addressed in the literature across three key dimensions—emotional orientation, self-efficacy, and behavioral performance—this concept reflects the extent to which individuals feel comfortable and competent in intercultural settings. In the context of tourism, intercultural interaction serves as a key indicator of the extent to which tourists internalize the lifestyle, history, and values of the society they visit (Fan et al., 2022).

With its rich historical heritage, diverse geography, and deep-rooted cultural traditions, Türkiye is a major destination visited by millions of foreign tourists every year. The communication skills of tour guides working on inbound tours to this destination directly impact not only the quality of individual tours but also the image of Turkish culture and tourism. Therefore, a thorough examination of tour guides' communication effectiveness is of great importance for both improving the quality standards of the tourism sector and strengthening intercultural dialogue. This study aims to make an original contribution to the existing literature in the fields of tour guiding, communication effectiveness, and intercultural interaction, and seeks to present findings of value from both academic and sectoral perspectives by developing practical recommendations.

1. Conceptual Framework

The World Federation of Tour Guide Associations (WFTGA) defines a tour guide as “a person who transports and introduces the cultural and natural heritage of a specific region to visitors in their preferred language, who specializes in a particular field, and who is authorized or recognized by official institutions” (WFTGA, 2025). The interpretation of local heritage, living culture, values, and cultural identity in general is recognized as a key component of contemporary tourist guiding. Tour guides distinguish themselves from other tourism professionals as individuals who establish a close rapport with tourists and engage in intensive, face-to-face communication, all while safeguarding the interests of sustainable tourism (Rabotic, 2010: 6).

It can be said that the tour guide plays the role of a cultural ambassador between the host community and tourists, and that the tour guide’s primary role is to transmit the host community’s culture to tourists (Huang, Hsu, and Chan, 2010: 30). Because tour guides are recognized as key players on the front lines of the tourism industry, they transform tourists’ visits from mere visual tours into meaningful experiences through their knowledge of destination attractions and culture, their interpretations, and their communication and service skills (Ap and Wong, 2001: 551).

The services produced by a tour guide are highly communication-intensive. For this reason, the quality of communication between tourists and the tour guide, the tour guide’s characteristics and performance, tourists’ perceptions of the tour’s quality, and, finally, tourists’ level of satisfaction with their vacation are of the utmost importance (Reisinger and Waryszak, 1994: 29).

Communication can be described as a phenomenon arising from the need of human beings, who are by nature social beings, to establish relationships, reach understanding, and exchange information with other people and entities in their environment (Ulusoy, 2012: 233). From the individual’s perspective, communication is a process. Each current experience and situation contains roots in the past and implications for the future. Whenever communication occurs at any given moment or in any given situation, both past experiences, accumulated knowledge, successes and failures, and misconceptions, as well as future expectations and hopes, become the subject of communication. Consequently, communication is a process that enables individuals to develop attitudes and behaviors based on their life experiences (Zilloğlu, 1993: 95). Individuals possess a special skill that helps them get away from disorder and establish order, better understand their environment, interact with others to achieve common goals, and make use of existing knowledge. This skill constitutes the individual’s capacity for high-level communication (Herbert, 1979: 420). Thus, communication can generally be determined as the mutual exchange of information, emotions, and thoughts occurring between two people in its narrowest sense, and among all people in its broadest sense (Ulusoy, 2012: 233). Humans differ from other living beings primarily through language, which allows them to describe and share their experiences using symbols. This is because humans can discover truths, develop knowledge, theories, and

general ideas and concepts. Consequently, they can transmit this information to others both now and in the future (Ford et al., 1988: 320).

Communication is viewed as a process that takes place within a context comprising the speaker, the listener, and the content of the message, and encompassing all of these elements (Çobanoğlu, 2002: 307). When the speaker and listener assume opposing yet complementary communicative roles, the communicative event encompasses everything the parties say and do and is an integral part of the event produced by their interaction (Georges, 1981: 245).

Establishing eye contact with the person or people you are communicating with—regardless of age, education, gender, or profession—focusing on them, and striving to understand them correctly are integral parts of effective listening. This approach communicates to the other party that they are valued and respected. Furthermore, paying attention to the other person's tone of voice, facial expressions, and body language during communication enhances our ability to empathize, which in turn makes communication more effective (Telman and Ünsal, 2005: 93). Consequently, this highlights the importance of the skill of narrating events that have become deeply ingrained within a culture. Effectively taking events to others gives the narrator the opportunity to relive the event even in their imagination; in this way, the narrator feels as though they have experienced an event they have never actually lived through, and thus others can also experience the event (Sütçü, 2013: 79).

Mancini (2001: 23) argues that the most important reason tourists prefer guided tours is that, despite the presence of technological devices at many attractions and historical sites, tour guides' lively narration offers greater motivation. Therefore, the fact that participants in guided tours expect tour guides to supply an engaging narrative that brings the stories to life in their imagination is also an indicator of the impact tour guides have on tour quality. In this way, the tour guide's engaging narration will contribute to detailed explanations of many topics of interest to the tourist group and, consequently, enhance tour quality. It will be possible to ensure quality in tour services given by tour guides who possess sufficient professional knowledge and expertise (Kara and Demir, 2021: 49). Consequently, tour guides are delineated as cultural ambassadors in their own destinations (Rabotic, 2010: 6).

A cultural ambassador is an actor who serves as a bridge between a destination and tourist cultures, helping to establish a balance between the two. The task of imparting information and promoting local cultural values and ways of life to tourists visiting the destination is generally entrusted to cultural ambassadors (Toker, 2011: 47).

Culture refers to the dynamic and complex environment that encompasses people's activities, worldviews, and beliefs, which are fundamentally enduring yet also capable of change within the context of routine communication and social interaction. In this context, culture involves the development of certain patterns, such as speech, dress, nutrition, and the preparation and consumption of food. It also encompasses many details that shape daily life, such as beliefs, belief systems, how time and space are structured, how people dance, and the values through which children are socialized (Lull, 2001: 95).

Culture is divided into specific categories. According to these distinctions, culture is explained as a collection of social heritage and traditions; the totality of practices and beliefs as well as material and spiritual elements that shape the structure of human existence and are acquired through a social process; the entire way of life of a society; the totality of how people adapt to their living conditions in terms of values, ideals, and behavior; educationally, as the behavioral patterns learned socially and transmitted to new generations through the same channels; and symbolically, as the organization of material and spiritual elements, behaviors, and emotions based on symbols (Boniface and Fowler, 1993:12). Interaction is outlined as individuals engaging in various experiences and forming relationships with others in their environment, thereby exchanging ideas. In this context, intercultural interaction refers to the tendency to engage with divergent cultural characteristics (Chen and Starosta, 2000: 18).

Intercultural interaction is described as the ability to recognize differences, respect them, and establish empathy (Menard–Warwick, 2009: 38); and as the skill of communicating effectively with individuals from unusual cultures in their own languages (Gökmen, 2005: 75). Intercultural interaction aims to help individuals establish a connection between their own culture and the target culture (Pegrum, 2008: 138).

Intercultural interaction is approached through three dimensions: intercultural sensitivity, intercultural awareness, and intercultural communication skills (Sercu, 2004: 76). Intercultural sensitivity refers to tolerance for cultures, values, and individuals, accepting them as they are. An individual's curiosity about disparate cultures, desire to understand and learn about them, and fostering positive emotions are factors that trigger cultural sensitivity. Intercultural sensitivity implies being sensitive and understanding toward cultural differences and the perspectives of individuals from various cultures (Chen, 1997: 5). Therefore, intercultural sensitivity, while addressing the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects of intercultural interaction, is primarily concerned with the emotional domain (Mercan, 2016: 1-13).

Intercultural awareness is the state of being aware of one's own cultural identity and others' cultural identities. Cultural awareness requires individuals to recognize their own biases and stereotypes and to work to overcome them. This enables individuals to be more conscious and open-minded in intercultural interactions (Deardorff, 2006: 257).

Intercultural communication skills refer to individuals' ability to communicate effectively and collaborate in intercultural interactions. Intercultural communication skills include language proficiency, active listening, conflict resolution, and adaptability. Intercultural communication skills enable individuals to interact successfully in diverse cultural contexts (Hammer et al., 2003: 425).

Cultural awareness plays a significant role among these three dimensions. This is because, to learn the target language, an individual must establish a connection between the source and target cultures, recognize similarities and differences, and develop an awareness of them. Therefore, this stage is essential for language learning. An individual open to

intercultural interaction can view their own culture and other cultures with a critical eye and develop an awareness of both the source and target cultures (Melanlıoğlu, 2013:131).

The role of a tour guide as a cultural ambassador encompasses intercultural mediation, cultural advocacy, and cultural friendship (Yu, Weiler, and Ham, 2002: 75). It can be said that the tour guide plays the role of a cultural ambassador between the host community and the tourists, and that the tour guide's fundamental role is to reflect the host community's culture to the tourists (Huang, Hsu, and Chan, 2010: 30). Indeed, tour guides are the individuals who describe the silent panorama visible through the bus window and deliver information about the places visited, photographed, and encountered. Tour guides typically serve as cultural mediators and interpreters between the local population and tourists. Therefore, tour guides' cultural and communication competencies play a significant role in intercultural interaction (Leclerc and Martin, 2004: 182).

When a tour guide leads a tour, they provide information according to a narrative plan organized in parallel with the tour itinerary. The narration delivered at each attraction is well-structured and tailored to the characteristics of the tourist group (Weiler and Ham, 2001: 557). The proper selection of information to be conducted and its transformation into an engaging narrative or interpretation can positively or negatively impact the tourists' experience during the tour. Therefore, not only the content of the information to be moved to tourists throughout the tour, but also how it is presented, is of great importance (Ababneh, 2018: 263).

Tour guides contribute in many ways to the cultural values they convey to tourists through their efforts. In this context, it should be emphasized that tour guides play a significant role in preserving and promoting cultural values and fostering intercultural exchange. Tour guides should be aware that they serve as cultural ambassadors for their countries and act accordingly. During the tour, the goal should not only be to gather information but also to contribute to the country's cultural values in every way. A professional tour guide should serve as a model in the preservation and promotion of their country's cultural values (Aslan and Çokal, 2016: 65).

2. Method

The primary objective of this study is to examine and demonstrate the impact of tour guides' levels of communication effectiveness on tourists' intercultural interaction processes in the context of incoming tours. In this regard, the concepts of communication effectiveness and intercultural interaction are explained in the conceptual framework section. The study's data were collected via a survey, a quantitative data collection method. The survey form, consisting of three sections, first includes participants' demographic information (gender, age group, marital status, nationality, number of visits to Türkiye, and travel companions). In the second section, the scale used in the study by Özbek and İskender (2021), titled "The Effect of Tour Guides' Narrative Performance on Tour Satisfaction: An Application in Cappadocia," was utilized to measure the communication effectiveness of tour guides. In the third section, three dimensions of the intercultural competence scale developed by Chao (2014), specifically those addressing interaction, were used to measure the level of intercultural interaction among

tourists participating in the relevant tours. The statements in the scales were rated using a 5-point Likert scale (1: Strongly disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Neither agree nor disagree, 4: Agree, 5: Strongly agree).

The data collection tool used in this study was designed to be administered both digitally via the Google Forms platform and in person. Accordingly, data collection was conducted in two separate formats: face-to-face interviews with participants and via the Google Forms platform. After the survey form was created, ethical committee approval was obtained from the Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences at Afyon Kocatepe University (Decision No. 2024/276) on August 21, 2024, prior to implementation, and the study was subsequently carried out. During data collection, physical survey forms were used for in-person interviews, while surveys administered via the Google Forms platform were distributed to participants via a QR code. This hybrid approach allowed participants to complete the survey using their preferred method, thereby enhancing data collection effectiveness and improving participant compliance.

The study population consists of foreign tourists who visit Antalya as part of incoming tours and participate in guided tours during their stay. This population presents a suitable framework for the study's objective, as it encompasses the interaction processes that tourists from diverse cultural backgrounds engage in under a tour guide's guidance. Given this population, a survey was conducted from September 25 to December 25, 2024. In total, the data was collected from 286 participants. However, the final dataset consists of the answers of 263 tourists selected from the population using simple random sampling. This method ensures that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected and increases the generalizability of the data obtained. It is accepted that the sample size is sufficient to meet the study's analytical requirements; based on the data collected from the participants, the relationships between tour guides' communication effectiveness and tourists' levels of intercultural interaction were examined.

During the analysis of the research data, validity (confirmatory factor analysis) and reliability analyses (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) were first conducted. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) for demographic information and the statements included in the scales were analyzed. Subsequently, relationship measurement analyses (correlation analysis) were performed, and a structural equation modeling program was utilized for impact measurement analyses.

3. Findings

In this study, which examines the impact of tour guides' communication effectiveness on tourists' levels of intercultural interaction, an exploratory factor analysis of the Intercultural Interaction Scale (IIS) was first conducted using data collected from participants. As presented in Table 1, the IIS used in this study has three sub-dimensions named emotional orientation, self-efficacy, and behavioral performance. These sub-dimensions account for 74.470% of the total variance, and emotional orientation is the most important. All sub-

dimensions have reliability coefficients above 0.70, indicating good reliability, where EO is 0.934, SE is 0.836, and BP is 0.864. Meanwhile, the factor loadings of 15 items of the IIS scale are higher than the critical value of 0.50. In sum, the IIS scale is valid based on an explanatory factor analysis in Table 1.

Table 1. Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Intercultural Interaction Scale

	Statements	Factor Loadings	Eigenvalue	Coefficient of determination	Cumulative variance	Reliability coefficient
Emotional orientation (EO)	EO1	0.783	4.299	33.073	33.073	0.934
	EO2	0.852				
	EO3	0.856				
	EO4	0.877				
	EO5	0.738				
Self-efficacy (SE)	SE1	0.571	3.106	23.892	56.965	0.836
	SE2	0.704				
	SE3	0.760				
Behavioral performance (BP)	BP3	0.528	2.276	17.505	74.470	0.864
	BP4	0.696				
	BP5	0.808				
	BP6	0.828				
	BP7	0.788				
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin coefficient						0.913
Bartlett's Sphericity Test						The value of χ^2 2535.543
						Degrees of freedom 78
						Significance level 0.000
						Scale Reliability 0.927

Note: The terms DY6, DP1, and DP2 were excluded from the analysis due to low factor loadings.

During the analysis of the research data, after conducting an exploratory factor analysis of the intercultural interaction scale, the dataset's validity was tested using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in a structural equation modeling program. Additionally, during this process, reliability was measured by calculating Cronbach's Alpha coefficient using statistical analysis software; the findings are presented in Table 2.

In scientific research, DFA enables the evaluation of each item's contribution to the scale as a whole and facilitates a more accurate assessment of scale reliability (Hair et al., 2022). The DFA results in Table 2 are presented along with measurement values, including SFY (standardized factor loadings), AVE (average variance extracted), and CR (composite reliability). Fornell and Larcker (1981: 45–46) note that if the AVE value is less than 0.50, construct validity may be questionable, and they recommend calculating the AVE value to assess convergent validity. Hair et al. (2022: 307) recommend using the CR value to measure internal consistency reliability and specify that the relevant value should be above 0.70. Hu and Bentler (1995: 83–85) also emphasize the evaluation of model fit using various fit indices. Researchers argue that values for GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index), NFI (Normalized Fit Index), CFI (Comparative Fit Index), and TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index) must be at least 0.90 to accept the model. RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) and SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) are other criteria in CFA (Hair et al., 2022: 323–324). While an RMSEA value of 0.08 indicates a reasonable level of model fit (Browne and

Cudeck, 1992: 13), an SRMR cutoff value close to 0.08 is acceptable for CFA modeling (Hu and Bentler, 1999: 27).

Table 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Communication Effectiveness and Intercultural Interaction Scales

	Statements	SFYλ	AVE	CR		Statements	SFYλ	AVE	CR
Emotional orientation	EO1	0.772	0.740	0.934	Communication Effectiveness	CE1	0.822	0.719	0.969
	EO2	0.861				CE2	0.806		
	EO3	0.918				CE3	0.859		
	EO4	0.932				CE4	0.868		
	EO5	0.808				CE5	0.841		
Self-efficacy	SE1	0.826	0.581	0.805		CE6	0.862		
	SE2	0.742				CE7	0.860		
	SE3	0.714				CE8	0.781		
Behavioral performance	BP3	0.510	0.569	0.865		CE9	0.840		
	BP4	0.700				CE10	0.855		
	BP5	0.768				CE11	0.891		
	BP6	0.884				CE12	0.889		
	BP7	0.850				CE13	0.890		
Scale reliability: 0.927						CE14	0.895		
Goodness of Fit						CE15	0.775		
Values	Observed Value	Critical value				CE16	0.855		
χ^2/df	2.107	≤ 5				CE17	0.834		
RMSEA	0.065	≤ 0.08				CE18	0.834		
GFI	0.929	≥ 0.90			Scale reliability: 0.979				
NFI	0.900	≥ 0.90			SFYλ: Standard factor load.				
CFI	0.945	≥ 0.90			AVE: Average Variance Extracted				
TLI	0.938	≥ 0.90			CR: Composite reliability				
SRMR	0.039	≤ 0.10			Obs. Val.: Observed Value				
$\chi^2: 874.349$ df: 415 p: 0.000					Crit. Val.: Critical value				

When the relevant values in Table 2 are evaluated in the context of the above explanations, it is observed that the DFA findings indicate reasonable model fit for all scales. The RMSEA value was calculated as 0.065; the GFI value was 0.929, the NFI value was 0.900, the CFI value was 0.945, and the TLI value was 0.938. On the other hand, the SRMR cut-off index indicates good model fit ($SRMR \leq 0.08$). When the research scales were evaluated in terms of AVE and CR, the emotional orientation AVE value for the cultural interaction scale was 0.740 and the CR value was 0.934; the self-efficacy AVE value was 0.581 and the CR value was 0.805; the behavioral performance AVE value was 0.569 and the CR value was 0.865; and for the communication effectiveness scale, the AVE value was 0.719 and the CR value was 0.969. When the findings of the DFA analysis regarding the research scales were evaluated overall, it was concluded that the dataset is valid. Finally, the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients in Table 2, which were above 0.70, confirmed the reliability of the research data.

After confirming the validity and reliability of the research data, descriptive analyses of the participants were conducted, and the findings are presented in Table 3. According to the findings, 165 of the 263 participants (63.1%) were women, and 162 participants (61.60%)

were single. The 25–34 age group accounted for the largest share at 34.22%, while the 18–24 age group (n: 74) was the second-largest.

Table 3. Results of Descriptive Analyses

Variable	Group	n	%	Variable	Group	n	%
Gender	Female	165	62.74	Nationality	English	105	39.92
	Male	98	37.26		German	57	21.67
Age Groups	18-24	74	28.14		Russian	18	6.84
	25-34	90	34.22		Polish	43	16.35
	35-44	49	18.63		Other	40	15.21
	45 and older	50	19.01		How many times have you visited Türkiye?	First	126
Marital Status	Single	162	61.60	Second		62	23.57
	Married	101	38.40	Third or more		75	28.52
				Who are you traveling with?	Alone	13	4.94
					With my family	140	53.23
					With my friends	110	41.83

According to Table 3, 162 participants (61.60%) were single and 101 (38.40%) were married. When their nationalities were examined, the largest group was British nationals (39.92%), while the smallest was Russian nationals (6.84%). When examining the number of times participants have visited Türkiye, 126 (47.91%) were first-time visitors, 62 (23.57%) were visiting for the second time, and 75 (28.52%) had visited at least three times. Finally, 53.23% of participants traveled with their families, while 41.83% traveled with friends. The proportion of those traveling alone is approximately 4.9%.

In the ongoing phase of the analysis of the research data, participants' levels of agreement with the statements on the scales were examined using arithmetic mean and standard deviation; furthermore, the degree of agreement for each statement was determined using frequency and percentage. In this context, participants' levels of agreement with the statements on the tour guide communication effectiveness scale and the intercultural interaction scale were evaluated, and the findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of Descriptive Analysis of the Items on the Scales

Variable	Statements	\bar{x}	s.d	Variable	Statements	\bar{x}	s.d
Emotional orientation	EO1	4.456	0.794	Communication Effectiveness	CE1	4.251	0.911
	EO2	4.483	0.833		CE2	4.125	1.024
	EO3	4.498	0.814		CE3	4.255	0.941
	EO4	4.498	0.791		CE4	4.270	0.924
	EO5	4.403	0.859		CE5	4.217	1.005
Overall average	4.468	0.728	CE6		4.316	0.893	
Self-efficacy	SE1	4.319	0.894		CE7	4.335	0.901
	SE2	4.179	0.966		CE8	4.217	1.005
	SE3	4.103	0.981		CE9	4.198	0.999
Overall average	4.200	0.822	CE10		4.319	0.939	
Behavioral performance	BP3	3.954	1.055		CE11	4.350	0.996
	BP4	4.091	0.924		CE12	4.262	0.967
	BP5	4.281	0.923		CE13	4.316	0.986
	BP6	4.255	0.941		CE14	4.312	0.946
	BP7	4.335	0.905		CE15	4.232	1.046
Overall average	4.183	0.765	CE16		4.346	0.944	
					CE17	4.266	0.991
					CE18	4.414	0.899
				Overall average	4.278	0.825	

An analysis of Table 4 reveals that participants' levels of engagement with the dimensions of the intercultural interaction scale are quite high. In this context, the level of engagement in emotional orientation was 4.468, the level of self-efficacy was 4.200, and the level of behavioral performance was 4.183. The statements with the highest participation levels on the intercultural interaction scale were, in order, \bar{x} : 4.498 "I am willing to understand individuals from divergent cultures" and \bar{x} : 4.498 "I am willing to communicate with people from contrasting cultures to broaden my worldview." On the other hand, the statement showing lower participation compared to others on the intercultural interaction scale is \bar{x} : 3.954: "I can use foreign languages functionally (in matters such as inviting, refusing, apologizing, etc.) to communicate effectively in intercultural settings." Furthermore, it was concluded that the statements on the intercultural interaction scale were perceived positively, and participants were highly satisfied with intercultural interaction.

When examining the communication effectiveness scale, another scale in the study, the overall average for participation was quite high at 4.278. Among the scale items, the statement "It was clear that the tour guide had prepared in advance for the topics he discussed" had the highest participation, with an average of \bar{x} : 4.414. This statement is followed, in order, by "The tour guide's presentation clearly demonstrated their interest and enthusiasm" (\bar{x} : 4.346) and "Thanks to the tour guide's presentation, I now know the places I visited better" (\bar{x} : 4.335). The statement that received the lowest level of agreement on the scale is \bar{x} : 4.125, "I gained new information thanks to the tour guide's presentation." As with the intercultural interaction scale, participants also demonstrated a high level of agreement with the statements on the communication effectiveness scale.

During the analysis of the research data, following descriptive analyses, a correlation analysis was first conducted for hypothesis testing, followed by path analysis using structural equation modeling software. In the correlation analysis phase, the Spearman correlation coefficient was used, and \sqrt{AVE} and HTMT values were calculated to test discriminant validity and convergent validity. The results of the correlation analysis regarding the research variables are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Correlation Values and Findings on Discriminant Validity

Variable	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	1	2	3	4
Emotional orientation (1)	4.468	0.728	0.740 ^a	0.809 ^b		
Self-efficacy (2)	4.200	0.822	.714 ^{**}	0.581 ^a	0.685 ^b	
Behavioral performance (3)	4.183	0.765	.560 ^{**}	.583 ^{**}	0.569 ^a	0.415 ^b
Communication Effectiveness (4)	4.278	0.825	.360 ^{**}	.399 ^{**}	.383 ^{**}	0.719 ^a

a: \sqrt{AVE} values. a>0.50

b: HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait) value. HTMT<0.90.

In light of the results of the correlation analysis presented in Table 5, significant relationships were found between communication effectiveness, the independent variable of the study, and the subdimensions of the intercultural interaction scale: emotional orientation ($r = 0.714$), self-efficacy ($r = 0.399$), and behavioral performance ($r = 0.383$). According to the table, the relationship between communication effectiveness and emotional orientation is high

($r > 0.60$), whereas those with the other variables are moderate ($r > 0.30$). Furthermore, the $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ values exceeding 0.50 indicate that convergent validity has been established. The HTMT threshold value used to test the discriminant validity of the research variables was 0.740. Henseler et al. (2015: 121) state that the HTMT threshold is the average of hetero-trait-hetero-method correlations (correlations between indicators in constructs measuring disparate phenomena) and note that HTMT thresholds equal to or lower than 0.90 are required to evaluate 95% sensitivity levels in terms of discriminant validity. In this context, the research variables exhibit discriminant validity.

Finally, to test the research hypothesis, a path analysis was conducted using structural equation modeling software, and the findings are presented in Figure 1. Based on the findings in Figure 1, the research model and the path analysis conducted within this framework (χ^2 : 1014.625, $p < 0.001$, RMSEA: 0.075; CFI: 0.927, NFI: 0.918) are statistically valid and reliable.

Figure 1. Path Analysis of Research Variables

According to the model shown in the figure, tour guides' communication effectiveness positively affects tourists' self-efficacy (46%), emotional performance (41%), and emotional orientation (37%). Furthermore, within the context of intercultural interaction, tour guides' communication effectiveness has a greater impact on the self-efficacy dimension than other variables. Consequently, effectively structuring the communication process between tour guides and tourists primarily contributes to building self-confidence and the ability to express oneself comfortably among the tourists participating in the tour. It is anticipated that tourists who can express themselves more comfortably may experience lower levels of neuroticism and exhibit positive emotional motivations or responses.

4. Discussion, Conclusions and Recommendations

The analysis of the research data reveals that, when tourists arriving in Türkiye on incoming tours participate in guided tours, the communication effectiveness of tour guides has a significant and meaningful impact on the tourists' levels of intercultural interaction. The values obtained from the exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses of the scales indicate that the measurement tools are satisfactory in terms of validity and reliability. This demonstrates that the research results are based on a sound statistical foundation.

When examining participants' average scores on the scales, a high level of participation is observed across the dimensions of the intercultural interaction scale (emotional orientation, self-efficacy, and behavioral performance). In particular, the high level of participation in the statements “understanding individuals from different cultures” and “being willing to communicate with peculiar cultures to broaden one’s worldview” indicates that tourists are open to intercultural learning and experiences. However, the relatively lower level of participation regarding the statement “being able to use foreign languages functionally” suggests that linguistic proficiency may pose a relative limitation in intercultural interaction.

The results regarding the communication effectiveness scale similarly reveal a high level of engagement. Participants emphasize that tour guides are well-prepared to convey information, that their presentations are engaging and enthusiastic, and that they offer participants new perspectives. However, the relatively lower average for the statement “gaining new information through the tour guide’s narration” suggests that participants may have differing expectations regarding the depth or originality of the information shown.

The results of the correlation analysis confirm significant relationships between communication effectiveness and the sub-dimensions of intercultural interaction. In this context, strong relationships were found between communication effectiveness and emotional orientation, while moderate relationships were identified with self-efficacy and behavioral performance. The path analysis findings support these results. It has been demonstrated that tour guides' communication effectiveness positively impacts tourists' self-efficacy (46%), behavioral performance (41%), and emotional orientation (37%). The high level of impact observed, particularly in the self-efficacy dimension, indicates that communication effectiveness directly contributes to tourists' ability to express themselves, move more comfortably in intercultural settings, and develop self-confidence.

The key findings are consistent with previous studies on the subject (Güdü, 2011; Şahin, 2012; Özdemir, 2016; Uslu, 2024). These studies emphasize that tour guides' communication skills have a decisive impact on the tourist experience; they highlight that tour guides who accompany tourists throughout their trips transform vacations from mere travel into enjoyable and unforgettable experiences. Additionally, acquiring new information, interacting with the local community, and sharing knowledge across cultures contribute to memorable experiences for tourists. In this context, it is evident that the literature supports the findings indicating that

tour guides' knowledge of local culture and their communication skills enrich tourists' experiences and positively influence their overall satisfaction levels.

An evaluation of the study's overall findings reveals that the communication effectiveness of tour guides is not limited to the mere transfer of information; rather, when they establish empathy-driven, positive, and effective communication with the group, positive changes occur in areas such as emotional orientation (the maintenance of positive motivations and attitudes toward the destination), self-efficacy (confidence in dealing with sundry cultures), and behavioral performance (adapting to a else culture, using the language effectively, etc.). This result also demonstrates that the quality of communication between the tour guide and the tourist is a decisive factor in the quality of the tour experience. Therefore, it is fair to say that the effectiveness of communication serves as a fundamental factor that facilitates intercultural interaction and enriches tourists' experiences.

The relevant study highlights the positive effects of effective communication on tourists. In this context, it is recommended that tour guides first research methods for communicating more effectively with tourists, conduct further research on empathy, and, during the tour, take questions into account as much as possible and furnish comprehensive answers at the appropriate time. Another recommendation is that tour guides plan their speech from start to finish before the tour begins, ensuring more effective communication without disrupting the flow of the tour.

The body of scientific knowledge on this subject should be expanded by increasing the number of studies that examine the research variables and by making comparisons.

In future studies, detailed analyses should be conducted by combining qualitative and quantitative research methods. Moreover, the study should be expanded to include a greater number of nationalities so that the issue can be evaluated from a broader perspective, and it should be determined whether there are differences among these nationalities.

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Appendix 1: Decision of the Committee on Research and Publication Ethics in the Social and Human Sciences at Afyon Kocatepe University

Evrak Tarih ve Sayısı: 21.08.2024-292622

T.C. AFYON KOCATEPE ÜNİVERSİTESİ SOSYAL VE BEŞERİ BİLİMLERİ BİLİMSEL ARAŞTIRMA VE YAYIN ETİĞİ KURULU KARARLARI	
TOPLANTI SAYISI:15	KARAR TARİHİ: 21.08.2024
KARAR 2024/276	
<p>Üniversitemiz Turizm Fakültesi öğretim elemanı Prof. Dr. Özcan ZORLU tarafından yürütülen (Diğer Araştırmacılar: Sibel ÇAMDİBİ), "Turist Rehberlerinin İletişim Etkinliğinin Kültürlerarası Etkileşim ve Kültürleşmeye Etkisi: Incoming Turlar Örneği" başlıklı yüksek lisans tezi kapsamında yapılan başvuruda yer alan veri toplama araçlarının, etik açıdan sakıncalı olmadığına, katılanların oy birliği ile karar verildi.</p>	
ASLI GİBİDİR	
Prof. Dr. Mustafa GÜLER Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimleri Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Kurul Başkanı	

The Effect of Tour Guides' Communication Effectiveness on Tourists' Intercultural Interaction Levels

Genişletilmiş Özet

Dünya Turist Rehberi Birlikleri Federasyonu'nun tanımına göre turist rehberi, belirli bir bölgenin kültürel ve doğal mirasını ziyaretçilere kendi tercih ettikleri dilde aktaran, alanında uzmanlaşmış ve resmi kurumlarca yetkilendirilmiş bir profesyoneldir (WFTGA, 2025). Gerçekleştirilen bu araştırmanın temel amacı, turist rehberlerinin sahip oldukları iletişim etkinliğinin turistlerin kültürlerarası etkileşim düzeyleri üzerindeki etkisini incoming turlar bağlamında bilimsel yöntemlerle ortaya koymaktır. Araştırma, Türkiye'ye gelen yabancı turistlerin rehber eşliğinde gerçekleştirdikleri kültürel deneyim sürecini ve bu süreçte rehberin iletişim performansının oynadığı belirleyici rolü incelemeyi kapsamaktadır. Türkiye, köklü kültürel birikimi ve zengin tarihsel mirasıyla her yıl milyonlarca yabancı ziyaretçiyi ağırlayan stratejik bir destinasyon konumundadır. Bu destinasyona yönelik incoming turlarda görev yapan turist rehberlerinin iletişim becerileri, yalnızca bireysel tur kalitesini değil, aynı zamanda Türk kültürünün yansıtılma biçimini ve ulusal turizm imajını da doğrudan etkilemektedir (Aslan ve Çokal, 2016). Araştırma, iletişim etkinliğinin kültürlerarası öğrenme çıktıları üzerindeki mekanizmasını ampirik olarak ortaya koyarak hem turizm eğitimi alanına hem de tur operatörlerinin uygulama pratiklerine yönelik kanıt temelli bir çerçeve sunmaktadır.

Literatür incelendiğinde turist rehberlerinin turizm endüstrisinin ön cephesinde yer alan ve destinasyon çekiciliklerini birer deneyime dönüştüren anahtar aktörler olarak konumlandığı görülmektedir (Ap ve Wong, 2001). Bu profesyonellerin ev sahibi toplum ile ziyaretçiler arasında kültürel aracı ve çevirmen işlevi gördüğü, dolayısıyla kültür elçisi olarak nitelendirildikleri vurgulanmaktadır (Rabotic, 2010). Huang, Hsu ve Chan (2010) ile Yu, Weiler ve Ham (2002) tarafından da belirtildiği gibi turist rehberinin temel rolü, ev sahibi toplumun kültürünü turistlere yansıtmak ve kültürlerarası aracılığı üstlenmektir. Turist rehberinin sunduğu hizmetlerin iletişim yoğun karakteri, hizmet kalitesinin doğrudan rehberin iletişimsel ve ilişkisel becerilerine bağlı olmasına yol açmaktadır (Reisinger ve Waryszak, 1994). Aslan ve Çokal (2016) ise profesyonel rehberlerin yalnızca bilgi aktaran kişiler değil, aynı zamanda ülkelerinin kültürel değerlerinin korunmasında ve tanıtımında örnek teşkil etmesi gereken aktörler olduğunu öne sürmektedir.

İletişim olgusu, bireyin sosyal varlık olarak diğer kişilerle ilişki kurma ve anlaşma ihtiyacından doğan, geçmiş yaşantıların ve gelecek beklentilerinin aktarımına aracılık eden bir süreç biçiminde tanımlanmaktadır (Ulusoy, 2012). Herbert (1979) ile Ford, Armandi ve Heaton (1988) iletişimi insanı diğer canlılardan ayıran özel bir beceri olarak tanımlamaktadır. İletişim etkinliği ise yalnızca içerik aktarımıyla sınırlı kalmayan, dinleyici farkındalığı, empati, beden dili, ses tonu ve kültürel duyarlılığı kapsayan çok boyutlu bir beceriler bütünüdür (Telman ve Ünsal, 2005). Georges (1981) iletişim etkinliğinin tarafların birbirini tamamlayan rolleriyle üretildiğini ileri sürmektedir. Tur rehberliği özelinde değerlendirildiğinde, etkili iletişim; canlı anlatım yoluyla turistin hayal gücünü harekete

geçiren, motivasyonunu sürdüren ve olgusal bilgiyi duygusal açıdan anlamlı bir deneyime dönüştüren bir performans olarak öne çıkmaktadır (Mancini, 2001). Kara ve Demir (2021) mesleki yeterliliği yüksek, etkili iletişim kuran rehberlerin sunduğu tur hizmetlerinin kalitesinin doğal olarak yükseldiğini ifade etmektedir.

Araştırmanın bağımlı değişkeni olan kültürlerarası etkileşim, bireylerin farklı kültürel değer sistemlerine yönelik geliştirdikleri farkındalık, duyarlılık ve uyum kapasitesini ifade etmektedir (Chen ve Starosta, 2000). Menard Warwick (2009) kültürlerarası etkileşimi farkındalıkların farkına varma, farklılıklara saygı gösterme ve empati kurma yeterliliği olarak tanımlarken Gökmen (2005) ile Pegrum (2008) bu kavramı bireyin kendi kültürüyle hedef kültür arasında bir ilişki kurma süreci olarak ele almaktadır. Literatürde söz konusu kavram; kültürlerarası duyarlılık, kültürlerarası farkındalık ve kültürlerarası iletişim becerisi olmak üzere üç temel boyutta incelenmekte (Sercu, 2004); turizm bağlamında ise duygusal yönelim, öz yeterlilik ve davranışsal performans alt boyutları üzerinden işlevselleştirilmektedir (Chao, 2014). Chen (1997) ile Mercan (2016) kültürlerarası duyarlılığı temel olarak duygusal alanla ilişkilendirirken Deardorff (2006) bu sürecin önyargı ve stereotiplerin aşılmasını gerektirdiğini vurgulamaktadır. Hammer, Bennett ve Wiseman (2003) ise kültürlerarası iletişim becerisinin dil becerileri, aktif dinleme, çatışma çözme ve uyum sağlama yeteneklerini içeren bir bütün olduğunu öne sürmektedir. Daha önce yürütülen çalışmalar rehberin yorumlama ve iletişim becerilerinin turistlerin kültürel anlamı içselleştirme süreçleri üzerinde belirleyici bir etkiye sahip olduğunu da ortaya koymaktadır (Leclerc ve Martin, 2004).

Araştırma kapsamında veriler, 25 Eylül 2024 ile 25 Aralık 2024 tarihleri arasında hem fiziksel anket formları aracılığıyla yüz yüze görüşmelerle hem de Google Forms platformu üzerinden QR kod yöntemiyle dijital olarak toplanmıştır. Uygulama öncesinde Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal ve Beşerî Bilimleri Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Kurulu'ndan 21.08.2024 tarih ve 2024/276 karar numarası ile etik kurul onayı alınmıştır. Araştırmada kullanılan anket formu üç bölümden oluşmaktadır. İlk bölüm katılımcıların cinsiyet, yaş grubu, medeni durum, milliyet, Türkiye'ye geliş sıklığı ve seyahat refakatçisi gibi demografik bilgilerini içermektedir. İkinci bölümde turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin ölçümü amacıyla Özbek ve İskender (2021) tarafından Kapadokya örneğinde geliştirilen ve toplam on sekiz ifadeden oluşan ölçek kullanılmıştır. Üçüncü bölümde ise kültürlerarası etkileşim düzeyinin ölçümünde Chao (2014) tarafından geliştirilen kültürlerarası yeterlilik ölçeğinin etkileşim odaklı üç boyutuna başvurulmuştur. Tüm ölçek ifadeleri 5'li Likert tipinde derecelendirilmiştir.

Araştırmanın evrenini, incoming turlar aracılığıyla Antalya destinasyonunu ziyaret eden ve rehberli turlara katılan yabancı turistler oluşturmaktadır. Bu evrenden basit tesadüfi örnekleme yöntemiyle seçilen 263 turistten veri elde edilmiştir. Verilerin analizi kapsamında ilk olarak ölçeklerin geçerliliği açımlayıcı faktör analizi ve doğrulayıcı faktör analizi ile değerlendirilmiş, güvenilirliği ise Cronbach alfa katsayısı ve kompozit güvenilirlik değerleri üzerinden test edilmiştir. Yakınsak geçerlilik için Fornell ve Larcker (1981) tarafından

önerilen \sqrt{AVE} değerleri, ayrışma geçerliliği için ise Henseler vd. (2015) tarafından önerilen HTMT eşik değeri kullanılmıştır. Devamında demografik değişkenlere ilişkin tanımlayıcı analizler yürütülmüş, değişkenler arasındaki ilişkiler Spearman korelasyon analiziyle incelenmiştir. Son olarak araştırma hipotezi, yapısal eşitlik modellemesi çerçevesinde yol analizi aracılığıyla sınanmış; model uyumu ise Hu ve Bentler (1995; 1999), Browne ve Cudeck (1992) ile Hair vd. (2022) tarafından önerilen kriterler doğrultusunda değerlendirilmiştir.

Araştırmada elde edilen tanımlayıcı bulgulara göre 263 katılımcının yüzde 62,74'ü kadın, yüzde 37,26'sı erkektir. Katılımcıların yüzde 61,60'ı bekar, yüzde 38,40'ı ise evlidir. Yaş gruplarına göre dağılımda 25 ile 34 yaş aralığı yüzde 34,22 ile en büyük grubu, 18 ile 24 yaş aralığı ise yüzde 28,14 ile ikinci büyük grubu oluşturmaktadır. Milliyetler incelendiğinde, İngilizler yüzde 39,92 ile en kalabalık ulusal segmenti, Almanlar ise yüzde 21,67 ile ikinci segmenti oluşturmaktadır. Katılımcıların yaklaşık yarısı (yüzde 47,91) Türkiye'ye ilk kez gelen turistlerden oluşmakta, yüzde 53,23'ü aileleriyle, yüzde 41,83'ü ise arkadaşlarıyla seyahat etmektedir.

Araştırma ölçeklerine ilişkin geçerlilik analizlerinde, Kültürlerarası Etkileşim Ölçeği'ne yönelik açımlayıcı faktör analizi sonucunda ölçeğin üç alt boyut içerdiği saptanmış ve hem alt boyutlar hem de ölçek düzeyinde güvenilirliğin sağlandığı görülmüştür. Bununla birlikte, faktör analizinde düşük faktör yükü gözlenen DY6, DP1 ve DP2 ifadeleri analizden çıkarılmıştır. Kültürlerarası Etkileşim Ölçeği'ne yönelik doğrulayıcı faktör analizi bulgularına göre modelin uyum iyiliği değerleri ($\chi^2/df = 2,107$, RMSEA = 0,065, GFI = 0,929, NFI = 0,900, CFI = 0,945, TLI = 0,938, SRMR = 0,039) literatürde önerilen ölçütleri karşılamaktadır (Hu ve Bentler, 1995).

Ölçeklere ilişkin yakınsak geçerlilik ve ayrışma geçerliliği kapsamında, İletişim Etkinliği ve Kültürlerarası Etkileşim Ölçeği boyutlarına ilişkin \sqrt{AVE} ve HTMT değerlerinin kriterleri karşıladığı saptanmıştır. Araştırma değişkenlerine yönelik korelasyon analizi bulgularına göre iletişim etkinliği ile duygusal yönelim arasında yüksek düzeyde anlamlı bir ilişki ($r = 0,714$), öz yeterlilik ile orta düzeyde anlamlı bir ilişki ($r = 0,399$) ve davranışsal performans ile orta düzeyde anlamlı bir ilişki ($r = 0,383$) saptanmıştır. Araştırma hipotezinin sınanmasında yapısal eşitlik modellemesi aracılığıyla yürütülen yol analizi bulgularına göre modelin uyum iyiliği değerleri istatistiksel açıdan kabul edilebilir düzeydedir ($\chi^2 = 1014,625$, $p < 0,001$, RMSEA = 0,075, CFI = 0,927, NFI = 0,918). Bulgular turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin turistlerin öz yeterlilik düzeyleri üzerinde yüzde 46, davranışsal performansları üzerinde yüzde 41 ve duygusal yönelimleri üzerinde yüzde 37 oranında olumlu ve anlamlı bir etkiye sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. En güçlü etkinin öz yeterlilik boyutunda gözlenmesi, etkili rehber ile turist arasındaki iletişim sürecinin turistlerin kendilerini ifade etme özgüvenini ve kültürel açıdan yabancı ortamlarda hareket etme yetkinliğini doğrudan beslediğine işaret etmektedir. Bu örüntü iletişim kalitesi yükseldikçe turistlerin kültürel kaygı düzeylerinin azalabileceğini ve etkileşim sürecinde daha olumlu duygusal tepkiler geliştirebileceğini de düşündürmektedir.

Elde edilen bulgular bir bütün olarak değerlendirildiğinde, turist rehberlerinin iletişim etkinliğinin Türkiye'ye incoming turlar aracılığıyla gelen yabancı turistlerin kültürlerarası etkileşim düzeyleri üzerinde anlamlı ve olumlu bir öncül değişken işlevi gördüğü açıkça ortaya çıkmaktadır. Söz konusu sonuçlar daha önce yürütülen ampirik araştırmaların bulgularıyla örtüşmekte (Güdü, 2011), Şahin (2012), Özdemir (2016) ile Uslu (2024) tarafından da vurgulandığı gibi turist rehberlerinin iletişim becerilerinin turist deneyimi üzerinde belirleyici bir rol oynadığı yargısını doğrulamaktadır. Bunun yanı sıra etki büyüklüklerinin farklılaşan örüntüsünü ortaya koyarak alanyazına özgün bir katkı sunmaktadır. Kuramsal açıdan çalışma, turist rehberinin kavramsal düzeyde sıkça vurgulanan kültürel aracı rolünü ampirik kanıtlarla pekiştirmesi bakımından önem taşımaktadır (Yu, Weiler ve Ham, 2002). Chao (2014) tarafından geliştirilen kültürlerarası yeterlilik ölçeği ile Özbek ve İskender (2021) tarafından geliştirilen iletişim etkinliği ölçeğinin yapısal eşitlik modellemesi çerçevesinde birlikte ele alınması, gelecekteki kültürlerarası hizmet araştırmaları için yeniden uygulanabilir bir analitik şablon ortaya koymaktadır. Etkinin en güçlü biçimde öz yeterlilik boyutunda, en zayıf biçimde ise duygusal yönelim boyutunda kendini göstermesi, hangi kültürlerarası çıktıların iletişimsel müdahaleye daha yatkın olduğuna ilişkin kuramsal tartışmayı zenginleştirmektedir.

Pratik ve sektörel açıdan bulgular tur operatörleri, meslek örgütleri ve turizm eğitimcileri için belirgin uygulama imaları içermektedir. İletişim etkinliğinin turistlerin özgüveni ve davranışsal uyumu üzerindeki birincil sürükleyici işlevi göz önüne alındığında, ileri düzey iletişim becerilerinin geliştirilmesi mesleki eğitim programlarına, hizmet içi gelişim faaliyetlerine ve profesyonel sertifikasyon süreçlerine sistematik biçimde yerleştirilmelidir. Yabancı dillerin işlevsel kullanımı boyutunda gözlenen göreceli düşük ortalama, çok uluslu ziyaretçi profili barındıran Antalya gibi destinasyonlarda görev yapan rehberler için çok dilli yetkinliğin stratejik bir tamamlayıcı beceri olduğunu vurgulamaktadır. Bu doğrultuda rehberlere turistlerle daha etkin iletişim yöntemleri üzerinde araştırma yapmaları, empatiyi geliştirici uygulamalara yönelmeleri ve tur akışını bozmayacak biçimde önceden iletişim planlaması yapmaları önerilmektedir.

Araştırma çeşitli sınırlılıklar barındırmakta olup bu sınırlılıklar aynı zamanda gelecek çalışmalar için yol gösterici niteliktedir. Verilerin yalnızca Antalya destinasyonundan toplanmış olması bulguların genellenebilirliğine ilişkin bir sınır oluşturmakta, gelecekte farklı destinasyonları kapsayan karşılaştırmalı tasarımların yürütülmesi önerilmektedir. Kesitsel desen yerine boylamsal ya da deneyim temelli tasarımların kullanılması, iletişim etkinliğinin kültürlerarası etkileşim üzerindeki etkisinin tur deneyiminin farklı aşamalarında ve tekrarlanan ziyaretlerde nasıl evrildiğini gösterme açısından değer taşıyacaktır. Farklı kaynak pazarlardan gelen turistleri kapsayacak uluslararası karşılaştırmalı araştırmalar, gözlenen etki büyüklüklerinin kültürel bağlama göre farklılaşp farklılaşmadığını ortaya koymaya yardımcı olabilecektir. Son olarak rehberler ve turistlerle yürütülecek niteliksel görüşmelerin nicel veriyle birlikte değerlendirileceği karma yöntem tasarımları, empati, anlatım hazırlığı ve

etkileşimsel duyarlılık gibi mikro düzeydeki iletişim mekanizmalarının kültürlerarası öğrenmeye nasıl dönüştüğünü daha derin bir biçimde aydınlayabilecektir.

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